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Basic Chinese Cosmology

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Here follows how I -hitherto - understand Chinese cosmology. My growth in understanding reflects self-guided study. I do not belong to any particular school. If I can illuminate some understanding of the classics I will. right: Norse Cosmology, not related but very cool.

The Basics

Chinese Cosmology is based on the Heavenly Branches and Earthly Stems, which in turn come from the animal zodiac and the basic yin and yang theory.

Yin is division and Earth, Yang is spirit and Heaven. So right from the name you know that everything has to do with Yin and Yang. Similar to the Mayan concept of three wheels of time each within the larger wheels comprising rotating epochs, the heavenly branches and earthly stems rotate.

Each day belongs to an element, yin or yang, and of course falls in an animal month, and all twelve **lunar** months happen in an animal year. There are 12 animals because there are 12 Earthly Branches.

When the calendar reaches the end of the solar year and time needs accounting for, the Chinese add a month that has no zodiac called "Ren Yue;" but other than this the months follow 30 day lengths (moon cycle is ~28-29 days).

See table:

Earthly Branch	Mandarin name	Japanese name		Korean name	Vietnamese name	Chinese zodiac	Direction	Season	Lunar Month	Double Hour
		On	Kun							

1	子	zǐ	し (shi)	ね(ne)	자 (ja)	tý (Tí)	Rat	0° (north)	winter	Month 11	11pm to 1am (midnight)
2	丑	chǒu	ちゅう う (chū)	うし (ushi)	축 (chuk)	sửu	Ox	30°		Month 12	1am to 3am
3	寅	yín	いん (in)	とら (tora)	인 (in)	dàn	Tiger	60°	spring	Month 1	3am to 5am
4	卯	mǎo	ぼう (bō)	う(u)	묘 (myo)	mǎo (mẹo)	Rabbit	90° (east)		Month 2	5am to 7am
5	辰	chén	しん (shin)	たつ (tatsu)	진 (jin)	thìn	Dragon	120°		Month 3	7am to 9 am
6	巳	sì	し (shi)	み(mi)	사 (sa)	ty	Snake	150°	summer	Month 4	9am to 11am
7	午	wǔ	ご(go)	うま (uma)	오 (o)	ngọ	Horse	180° (south)		Month 5	11am to 1pm (noon)
8	未	wèi	び(bi)	ひつじ (hitsuji)	미 (mi)	mùi	Goat	210°		Month 6	1pm to 3pm
9	申	shēn	しん (shin)	さる (saru)	신 (sin)	thân	Monkey	240°	autumn	Month 7	3pm to 5pm
10	酉	yǒu	ゆう (yū)	とり (tori)	유 (yu)	dậu	Rooster	270° (west)		Month 8	5pm to 7pm
11	戌	xū	じゅう つ (jutsu)	いぬ (inu)	술 (sul)	tuất	Dog	300°		Month 9	7pm to 9pm
12	亥	hài	がい (gai)	い(i)	해 (hae)	hợi	Pig	330°	winter	Month 10	9pm to 11pm

As this indicates the cycle starts with Rat and goes to Pig. 2012 is Dragon, so chen is its earthly branch. Today being 2/20 that means that this is the month of the Rat because Chinese New Year only recently occurred. Remember it is a lunar calendar.

Now, there are ten Heavenly Stems, an ancient Shang era system for creating days of the week. When these are multiplied together they produce a 60 day cycle because the 5 elements are multiplied across the 12 branches on the yang side before switching to the yin side. $12 \times 5 = 60$.

	Celestial Stem	Chinese Pinyin	Japanese kunyomi	Japanese on'yomi	Korean (RR)	Vietnamese	Yin and Yang (陰陽)	Wu Xing (五行)	Wu xing correlations
1	甲	jiǎ	kinoe	kō	갑 (gap)	giáp	陽 (yang)	木 (wood)	東 East
2	乙	yǐ	kinoto	otsu	을 (eul)	át	陰 (yin)		
3	丙	bǐng	hinoe	hei	병 (byeong)	bính	陽 (yang)	火 (fire)	南 South
4	丁	dīng	hinoto	tei	정 (jeong)	đinh	陰 (yin)		
5	戊	wù	tsuchinoe	bo	무 (mu)	mậu	陽 (yang)	土 (earth)	中 Middle
6	己	jǐ	tsuchinoto	ki	기 (gi)	kỷ	陰 (yin)		

7	庚	gēng	kanoe	kō	경 (gyeong)	canh	陽 (yang)	金 (metal)	西 West
8	辛	xīn	kanoto	shin	신 (sin)	tân	陰 (yin)		
9	壬	rén	mizunoe	jin	임 (im)	nhâm	陽 (yang)	水 (water)	北 North
10	癸	guǐ	mizunoto	ki	계 (gye)	quý	陰 (yin)		

To find out a year's number, you can use the steps in the Wiki article reproduced on the right.

Now, more important than the year or month is the energetic aspect of the day and even the hour.

The hours of a day are also divided into the Earthly Branches using again the animal zodiac, but more importantly have been correlated to the flow of the internal organs and channels' Qi. This means that one can know what the general energetic influences upon and in benefit to any particular aspect of the individual by recognizing the time, day-type, and overall then the date; as well as looking at the alignment of far off celestial bodies.

That is the order of importance because the larger celestial objects have weak pull as compared to the moon, sun, and nearby planets. Mercury, for example, is very small and also very close to the sun and its effect is quite weak as compared to the effect of Jupiter which is massive. Yet Mars and Venus have more effect, but not as much as our nearest neighbor and controller of tides and human emotional and physiological cycles: the moon. The Moon is yin and the Sun is yang. These two constitute the largest extra-terrestrial forces *by far*. However on earth the effect of yin and yang polar forces are also present.

The key to understanding things though is that everything works in "cohorts." Depending on the effect you are curious about, one must consider the level of cohort.

A society may have a yang day while another society has a yin day. Indeed some cultures are rising for the day while others are going to bed. This too, within the country some parts

may have yang days and others yin days. And this is true too some friends may be having yang days and others yin days.

Text Box

Thus, to find out the **Gregorian** year's equivalent in the Sexagenary cycle use the appropriate method below.

1. For any year number greater than 4 AD, the equivalent Sexagenary year can be found by subtracting 3 from the Gregorian year, dividing by 60 and taking the **remainder**. See example below.
2. For any year before 1 AD, the equivalent Sexagenary year can be found by adding 2 to the Gregorian year number (in BC), dividing it by 60, and subtracting the remainder from 60. See example below.
3. 1 AD, 2 AD and 3 AD correspond respectively to the 58th, 59th and 60th years of the Sexagenary cycle then.

The result will produce a number between 0 and 60, corresponding to the year order in the cycle; if the remainder is 0, it corresponds to the 60th year

And of course then it is up to each individual to determine where their energy falls in relation - vibrationally and spatially - to the larger energetic forces surrounding them: of friends, of society, or the world at large. For instance a person with fast-cycle type bipolarism will find they have a difficult time remaining on the same track energetically with the larger part of society. This means that their yin/yang cycles are different than the typical 1 per day as described above.

Now after this there is also the hexagram of the day to consider. This hexagram is based primarily on the prevailing energy of the day, and yet also upon the season and the date. But since the only way to acquire the hexagram (legitimately, not through an internet portal) is through one's own tossing, and each person has an individual toss for themselves, then there is no repeated, predictable form to this. Some hexagrams may last only a few hours as pertaining to a date, while the hexagram it flows into through the change may last days.

What is a hexagram?

A hexagram is a yin yang combination of two trigrams. A trigram is a three line representation of relative yin and yang properties in each of the 8 prime laws as correlating to Heaven, Man, and Earth. This triple plane system, when doubled as a yin (inner) and yang (outer) form a hexagram, and by math there are 64 of these.

A hexagram also has changing lines as represented by minimal yin and maximal yang. When this happens they can invert themselves and the energy of the Universe flows (Dao in motion) into a new hexagram that is both informed by and yet distinct from the previous. On top of this there is a way of deriving the CORE energy from said hexagram and forming a new hexagram.

How to toss the Yi Jing is not the subject of this article, and one should attend a class to understand it.

The point is to understand what all these energies really mean.

Our body is surrounded by matter, electromagnetic energy, gravity, and inundated by radiation as well as many unknown effects from Dark Energy, Dark Matter, and even the Vacuum's energy. On top of this the psyche has a hitherto unexplored field of energy and should be understood to be a force upon us. Yet all of these things have something in common: the Law of Polarity or Yin and Yang.

If this is true then we may begin to see that how we approach and are approached by the world daily can reflect not necessarily a "fated" interaction (after all there is still the Chaotic principle of the Law of Evolution), but at least some form of "providence." That some actions will meet

of a cycle. Thus, using the first method, the equivalent Sexagenary year for 2012 AD is the 29th year (壬辰; *rén-chén*), as $(2012-3) \bmod 60 = 29$ (i.e. the remainder of (2012-3) divided by 60 is 29). Using the second, the equivalent Sexagenary year for 221 BC is the 17th year (庚辰; *gēng-chén*), as $60 - [(221+2) \bmod 60] = 17$ (i.e. 60 minus the remainder of (221+2) divided by 60 is 17).

Examples

Step by step example to determine the sign for 1967:

1. $1967 - 3 = 1964$
("subtracting 3 from the Gregorian year")
2. $1964 \div 60 = 32$ ("divide by 60 and discard any fraction")
3. $1964 - (60 \times 32) = 44$
("taking the **remainder**")
4. 44 = Fire Sheep (丁未; *dīng-wèi*), see table.

Step by step example to determine the cyclic year of first year of the reign of **Qin Shi Huang** (246 BC)

1. $246 + 2 = 248$ ("adding 2 to the Gregorian year number (in BC)")
2. $248 \div 60 = 4$ ("divide by 60 and discard any fraction")
3. $248 - (60 \times 4) = 8$ ("taking the **remainder**")
4. $60 - 8 = 52$ ("subtract the remainder from 60")
5. 52 = Wood Rabbit (乙卯; *yǐ-mǎo*), see table.

with more success because of favorable circumstances than other actions will that meet with unfavorable circumstances.

By using the Yi Jing, and paying attention to these forces, the Sage - or at least an adept individual - will discern and be able to guard against negative impacts to the psyche by knowing when to avoid an action or when to engage in it. This is basically the thinking and the reason for use.

The Chaos Effect

Unfortunately it appears that things may not - even in rotation - follow a linear path. A hexagram may progress out to another and then flow back in upon itself... or be carried for for an extreme portion of time, or be so short as to be considered skipped altogether. Also yang days can follow yang days and vice versa. Or wood can, instead of flowing into fire, flow into water, its mother.

These effects are what provide "ripple" to the data stream and make "pulse reading" the Dao very difficult, and yet also very fun. Of course it isn't fun if we misread the day and feel it is a good day to go out and do something energetic and instead it turns sour on us. I recently, for example, started off very excited to go out and play basketball and not only had a ankle sprain but also received **terrible** news that day. Luckily my humor remained. But the point is that even in paying attention to one's inner rhythms one can misread the Dao. It is worth noting I had not consulted to oracle about playing basketball, so we will never know if the event was technically preventable, but I like to believe it was and hopefully I was not "fated."

The Main Point

The thing to take away from Chinese Cosmology (Astrology and Numerology) is that it has wisdom, fun, and utility in our daily lives. It is, of course, nothing to become obsessed about. At one time in Chinese history the people would do nothing from going on trips to even burying the dead without calculating a good day. This was very interesting because they also had no precise way to measure the minutes or seconds of the clock, so there was a dichotomy that may reflect some level of superstition. As a scientific society we want to respect the fact of cosmological forces without being tied down to a dogmatic ritual. Rituals and rites are the backbone of a good traditional society, but can also keep a society backwards in its thinking, and unable to obey the changes required in adaptation by the Law of Evolution. In observing any ritual - from tossing the Yi Jing to reading a fortune cookie, one should take the omens and oracles with some measure of truth and seriousness, and yet also light-heartedly. After all, quantum physics has taught us that just because something appears one way or likely to be one way doesn't mean it is a certainty, it may in fact be the **uncertainty** that is most true and most probable. In this way, perhaps, Godhead hopes to play us all for fools to teach us humility.